

New challenges on façade insulation systems with superinsulation materials

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Roberto Garay Martinez
TECNALIA, Sustainable Construction Division
Roberto.garay@tecnalía.com

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Heat balance of buildings

Heat flows in buildings are highly variable, depending on parameters such as:

- *Latitude*
- *Date of construction*
- *Building type, shape*
- *User behavior*

But, although not perfect, some figures are still needed to put façade insulation in context.

Typical energy losses in dwellings

Multi-rise building in Warsaw, renovated fenestration

Typical energy losses in dwellings

Multi-rise building in Warsaw, renovated fenestration

Multi-rise building in Warsaw, renovated envelope

Multi-rise building in Warsaw, renovated envelope + ventilation system (50%)

Multi-rise building in Warsaw, renovated envelope + ventilation system (50%) + most performing fenestration

Typical energy loss share of residential buildings

Within the heat balance of a building, transmission losses through walls:

- *Are 15-26% of the total heat losses*
- *Are quite similar independently latitude*
- *Can be reduced up to 50% through refurbishment*

Fenestration is the weak point in insulation technology:

- *Up to 65% of the total heat loss*
- *Technological limits to U-value reduction*

Façade insulation systems

Why?

Heat transfer through façades can be reduced through insulation:

External

Cavity

Internal

Systems can be categorized in two subsystems:

Wet

Dry

Location:

External: ETHICS, ventilated façades, ...

Cavity: Foam injection in the cavity, ...

Internal: Plasterboard based systems

System type:

Wet: Mortar/cement based systems

Dry: Profiles are used to fix the cladding and/or the insulation elements.

Thermal bridging in dry insulation systems

In commonly used dry construction systems, materials are fixed to load bearing elements by an arrangement of profile elements.

These systems are commonly made of two materials:

- *Metal profiles (Cold rolled Steel, extruded aluminium)*
- *Wooden studs*

Any of these materials is clearly more conductive than insulation materials.

Profile/stud systems are:

- *Laid across the insulation system*
- *Made of materials with higher thermal transmissivity*

Some properties:

- *In metal stud systems:*
 - *stud/insulation conduction ratio: 1000:1*
 - *Profile thickness: <1 mm*
- *In Wood stud systems:*
 - *the stud/insulation conduction ratio: 10:1*
 - *Stud thickness: 3-5 cm*

Relative relevance of thermal bridge of profile systems:

- *The thermal bridge effect of profiles in dry construction systems increases with insulation thickness*
- *It depends on the thermal conductivity ratio & profile thickness*

With state of the art insulation materials, 25-40mW/mK

- High U values ($>0,5W/m^2K$): 20% of the insulation capacity is lost
- Low U values ($<0,2W/m^2K$): Over 40% of the insulation capacity is lost

With state of the art insulation materials, 25-40mW/mK

When superinsulation materials are used:

- The stud/insulation conduction ratio is increased*
- Thermal bridges increase in relevance for the same insulation thicknesses*
- However the Relative Insulation Ratio is similar for equal U-values*

Reasonable insulation levels for high performing insulation materials:

- $U < 0,5 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$ ■
- Minimum insulation thickness: 3-5cm ■

Within these ranges, the thermal bridge effect increases the total heat transfer by 25-30% ■

Alternative materials

State of The Art

- **Metal** is highly conductive but only small sections are needed.
- The insulation level of **Wood** is fairly good, but large sections are needed.

New alternatives with Composite materials:

- Small sections
- Fairly good insulation level

Source: <http://www.topglass.com>

Meta-Analysis of alternatives

- Three materials
{Steel, Wood, Composite}
- Several Shapes
{Metal & composite: C, Z, L; Wood: Thick, Narrow}
- Several arrangements
{One layer, two layers, three layers, crossed configurations, ...}

Results

- Good thermal designs can be achieved with all three materials
- *Good thermal designs in metal & wood require of complex, & expensive configurations (3 layers, crossed,...)*
- *All evaluated solutions with composite materials are better insulated than with any other material*

Before

How

After

Conclusions

- *Heat transfer through the opaque envelope accounts for 15-26% of the total heat losses of a building.*
- *There is a trend into increasing the insulation level of buildings.*
- *A large share of insulation systems (dry systems) rely on profile solutions to provide mechanical stability. These systems are predominant within internal insulation solutions.*
- *Within dry insulation systems, **thermal bridging through profile systems can reduce the insulation level over 25%***
- *Alternative materials, such as **composites**, produce **better insulation solutions.***

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